

Isomorphism of Turing Automata Output and Regular Languages

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ABSTRACT

In this short message, we are to address the output, produced by the Turing tape automaton, or Turing Machine, which is further divided as deterministic and non-deterministic, to the set of regular languages recognized by finite automata.

DEFINITION

Since each of the Turing machines [1] has a limited set of states during which it can transit to the next step, or iteration, of processing the input and, thus, going to the halting or accepting, or rejecting, state, we are to define the set of words which are written are well-defined as programs produced by this machine.

The regular language [2] is formed from the Deterministic Turing Machine (DTM) or Non-deterministic Turing Machine (NDTM) can arbitrarily produce the regular set of languages, known as programs of this machines according to the finite state of states in the transition diagram as it can be seen in various sources [3].

On the account of "P versus NP" theorem [4] we are to define the proved equality of P and NP-classes of complexity as Finite Automata (FA) are isomorphic with respect to the regular language they accept [5].

CONCLUSION

We have come to the end of the "P versus NP" continued story and the positive output of the proof of equivalence of these complexity classes gives the horizons of the universality of automata and their isomorphic properties as well.

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